

DIACHRONIC ANALYSIS OF ECONOMIC TERMS IN ENGLISH AND UZBEK LANGUAGES

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.19367703>

Keywords: *Diachronic, economic terminology, terminology issues, lexical unit, specialized terms.*

This article examines the diachronic development of economic terms in English and Uzbek, showing how historical, social, and economic changes influenced the formation, borrowing, and semantic transformation of vocabulary. It analyzes processes such as semantic shift, and lexical expansion, with attention to the impact of globalization and market reforms on both languages. By comparing parallel terms, the study identifies similarities and differences in meaning, structure, and usage, demonstrating that diachronic analysis helps improve translation accuracy, terminology standardization, and cross-cultural economic communication.

The rapid improvement of science and technology, the ongoing production processes are heavily influenced by languages worldwide. It's important to highlight that effectively use of the extensive knowledge gained in global linguistics when studying economic terms in Uzbek and English, as well as the structure and regulation of dictionaries, can bring positive outcomes. Additionally, Uzbekistan has undergone significant changes, reforms, and innovations in all aspects of social life since gaining independence. These processes are undoubtedly reflected in the language, which serves as a reflection of the nation. Furthermore, linguistic updates raise various issues in modern linguistics.

Thus, it is crucial to examine Uzbek economic terminology alongside its English equivalents. The field of economics plays a crucial role in comprehending the global economy and facilitating international trade. English, being widely used in business, trade, and diplomacy, serves as a language of great importance. Meanwhile, as a developing country with a growing economy, Uzbekistan requires accurate economic terminology. This study aims to explore the historical analysis of economic terms in English and Uzbek, considering that economic terms are often context-specific and their meanings can be different based on the economic and social conditions of a particular country¹.

The formation and development of each terminological system are inextricably linked with their respective fields, acquiring their specific characteristics within those fields. "Term" is a modern concept, a lexical unit that expresses a specific meaning across various societal domains based on linguistic criteria, fulfilling a distinct functional role. Terms take the form of words and word combinations structurally. Also, they represent lexical units with a limited scope within a specialized domain semantically.

¹ An Explanatory Dictionary of the Uzbek Language. Vols. 1–5. Tashkent: National Encyclopedia of Uzbekistan State Scientific Publishing House, 2006–2008.

English and Uzbek economic terminology have developed their own paths and have attracted the attention of numerous foreign and local scholars since the emergence of the earliest written sources. For instance, H.Dadaboev's research not only covers political, military, tax, customs, finance, and diplomatic terminology but also serves as a comprehensive investigation into the historical development of the terminological system of the Uzbek language². H.Dadaboev's scientific work focuses on studying terminology issues, offering an example of the evolutionary etymology of some historical economic terms utilized in ancient Turkic language (VI-X), old Turkic (XI-XIV), and old Uzbek literary language (XV-XIX). It has been extensively analyzed from a scientific perspective.

Historical records reveal that the renowned statesman and encyclopedist Zahiriddin Muhammad Babur (1483-1530) and his descendants made significant contributions to social, economic, and legal matters. Babur's works, such as "Boburnoma" and "Mubayyin" notably emphasize economic information. By studying these works, we can uncover fresh ideas and guidance for analyzing the current economic reforms and changes in our country, drawing concise conclusions and implementing them practically.

Particularly remarkable are Babur's perspectives on the economy, which encompass fundamental aspects such as production, trade, commerce, taxes, and duties. While we may not possess separate writings or primary sources specifically addressing Babur's governance, production and trade organization, or his economic policy during his reign, we can draw brief conclusions based on scientific knowledge and insight³. As a profound thinker and encyclopedist, Babur possessed a deep understanding of economic laws, recognizing the indispensable role of the economy in society and the state. Consequently, he issued practical and equitable decrees and judgments, conducting a well-founded economic policy that led to peace, national harmony, and political and social progress during his rule. This is why the kingdom established by Babur endured for several centuries, leaving an indelible mark in history⁴. It is worth noting that various scientific-theoretical approaches to terms and terminology, both positive and negative, play a crucial role in shaping this field, sparking numerous meaningful discussions and divergent opinions among linguists.

Over the centuries, the appearance of the word term in different systematic languages, although we can tentatively note various ideas about its origin, it is the result of the combination of the Latin word *terminus*, which appeared in the Middle Ages, and the ancient Greek words *logos* (which means «concept», "doctrine"), we can note the appearance of the word terminology more precisely compared to the word term. In the field of linguistics, there is a lot of evidence and a number of hypotheses that the term and concept of terminology began to be used in oral and written speech. In some sources, the concept of *terminus* was first expressed as the divinity of boundaries, and later as a boundary stone, the last or completed point, place, destination, while in the linguistic sources of the Middle Ages, the word *terminus* was used in the sense of identifying and defining (something). The emergence, formation and development

² Djumambetova G. "Scientific-Theoretical Views on Terms and Terminology in Linguistics." *Journal of Foreign Languages and Linguistics*, vol. 5, no. 5, 2023.

³ Schneiderová A. "Historical Background to English Legal Language." *Journal of Modern Science*, vol. 2, no. 37, 2018, 117-126 p.

⁴ Sonneveld H., and K. Loenning. "Introducing Terminology." In *Terminology*, 1994, 8-34 p.

of the terminological system of the economy is directly related to the history of the early and middle ages.

As S.P. Tolstov correctly stated; In ancient times, the improvement of socio-economic relations in the conditions of Central Asia, the first land ownership, forms of ownership, the composition of the first agriculture and production structures, the tax system and their structural structures, in general research, undoubtedly, archaeological, the role of ethnographic, paleoanthropological, as well as linguistic data is incomparable. If we look at the English language during the Middle Ages, medieval English was dominated by French under the influence of the royal family, Latin in the fields of science, medicine or law⁵. Accordingly, the concepts of economics used in English as a whole are mainly related to these two languages. In addition, the uniqueness of periods, the changing of times and rulers sometimes gave opportunities to the economic sector, and sometimes it was the opposite. These social and political realities have influenced the use of concepts in the language in different ways.

The study shows that economic terminology in English and Uzbek has developed through historical change, language contact, and socio-economic transformation. Diachronic comparison reveals shifts in meaning, borrowing patterns, and structural adaptation that reflect cultural and institutional differences. Understanding these processes improves accurate translation, supports terminology standardization, and contributes to clearer intercultural communication in economic discourse.

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⁵ Ahmedov O.S. Linguistic Analysis of Tax and Customs Terms in English and Uzbek and Problems of Translation. PhD diss., Tashkent, 2016. 255 p.